

		Standard Operating Procedure SOP-AVITHRAPID
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Valid from:	2026-05-20	

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1. Purpose

This Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) describes the standardized method for the evaluation of antiviral activity of investigational compounds within the AVITHRAPID project. The procedure is designed to assess the susceptibility of viral strains to compounds with potential antiviral activity against different flaviviruses (Zika virus, ZIKV; Dengue virus, DENV; West Nile virus, WNV) and SARS-CoV-2.

2. Scope

This SOP applies to cell-based antiviral assays performed for research purposes. The assay evaluates viral replication using different readouts depending on the virus and cell line:

- DENV, ZIKV, and WNV: ELISA-based detection of the viral envelope (E) protein in infected cells.
- SARS-CoV-2:
 - Using VERO cells: assessment of cytopathic effect (CPE) via CellTiter assay.
 - Using A549-AT cells: ELISA-based detection of the viral nucleocapsid (N) protein.

3. Responsibilities

3.1. Laboratory Personnel

Personnel are responsible for the correct execution of the antiviral assay, adherence to biosafety requirements, and accurate recording of experimental data.

3.2. Study Manager

The Study Manager supervises the execution of the SOP, reviews data, and ensures compliance with quality standards.

4. Materials and Equipment

4.1. Cell Lines

- Huh-7 human hepatoma cells (#JCRB0403 from JCRB Cell Bank)
- A549-hACE2-TMPRSS2 cell line (#a549-hace2tpsa from InvivoGen)
- VERO E6 cells (#CRL-1586 from ATCC)

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4.2. Viruses

- Dengue virus, serotype 1 and 2 (DENV-1 and -2)
- ZIKV, H/PF/2013 (Asian lineage)
- WNV, Italy/2009 strain
- SARS-CoV-2 B.1 variant

4.3. Reagents and Materials

- DMEM High Glucose (cod. ECM0728L, Euroclone) supplemented with Fetal Bovine Serum South America origin EU 1% (cod. ECS5000L, Euroclone), Penicillin/Streptomycin 1% (cod. ECB3001D, Euroclone), referred as “complete DMEM”
- Reference compounds: Sofosbuvir (cod. HY-15005, DBA), Nirmatrelvir (cod. HY-138687, DBA)
- P-gp inhibitor CP-100356 hydrochloride (cat. HY-108347, DBA)
- Test Compound(s)
- CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 (cod. G9242, Promega)
- Formaldehyde 10% (cod. 526912, Carlo Erba Reagents)
- Triton X-100 (cod. FC72104100000, Carlo Erba Reagents)
- Tween-20 (cod. FC72109100000, Carlo Erba Reagents)
- Bovine Serum Albumin (BSA) (cod. A7030, Sigma)
- 3,3',5,5'-Tetramethylbenzidine (TMB) (cod. T8665, Sigma)
- Sulphuric Acid (H₂SO₄) 0.5 M (cod. 410577000, Carlo Erba Reagents)
- Flavivirus detection: Anti-Flavivirus group ag mAb 4G2 (cod. NPB2-52709, Novus Bio)
- SARS-CoV-2 detection: SARS Nucleocapsid Protein Antibody (cod. NPB2-9052709, Novus Bio)
- Secondary antibody: Goat anti-Mouse IgG (H+L) HRP (cod. NB7570, Novus Bio)
- White 96-well plates suitable for luminescence detection
- Adjustable pipettes and sterile consumables

4.4. Equipment

- CO₂ incubator (37°C, 5% CO₂)
- Class II biological safety cabinet
- Phase contrast microscope
- GloMax® Discover Microplate Reader (Promega)
- Orbital shaker

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5. Procedure

5.1. Cell Seeding and Compound Preparation

- Seed 6,000 cells/well in 96-well plates (Huh-7, A549-AT, VERO E6)
- Prepare three-point serial 4-fold dilutions of investigational compounds starting from the highest non-cytotoxic concentration as determined by prior cytotoxicity assays
- Include appropriate reference compounds, i.e. Sofosbuvir for flaviviruses and Nirmatrelvir for SARS-CoV-2, tested starting from 20 μ M and 1 μ M, respectively, together with untreated infected and uninfected controls.

5.2. Infection and Treatment

5.2.1. Flaviviruses infection

- DAY 0:
 - Early morning: Seed 6,000 cells/well in 96-well plates
 - Late afternoon: Pre-incubate compounds with cells for 16 h at 37°C, 5% CO₂
- DAY 1: Remove compounds, infect cells with DENV-2 (M.O.I. = 0.04) for 1 h. Replace medium with compounds and controls, incubate 72 h at 37°C, 5% CO₂
- DAY 5: Perform Immunodetection Assay

5.2.2. SARS-CoV-2 infection

5.2.2.1. A549-AT cells

- DAY 0:
 - Early morning: Seed 6,000 cells/well in 96-well plates
 - Late afternoon: Pre-incubate compounds with cells for 16 h at 37°C, 5% CO₂
- DAY 1: Remove compounds, add SARS-CoV-2 (M.O.I. = 0.005) with fresh compounds and controls, incubate 72 h at 37°C, 5% CO₂
- DAY 5: Perform Immunodetection Assay

5.2.2.2. VERO E6 cells

- DAY 0: Seed 6,000 cells/well in 96-well plates
- DAY 1: Add compounds to cells in the presence of the P-gp inhibitor CP-100356 hydrochloride (0.5 μ M) and incubate for 1 h at 37°C and 5% CO₂
- Infect cells with SARS-CoV-2 (M.O.I. = 0.004)
- Incubate plates for 72 h at 37°C and 5% CO₂
- DAY 5: Perform CellTiter assay

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5.3. Detection of Viral Replication

5.3.1. Immunodetection Assay (ELISA-based)

- Fix cells with formaldehyde 10% for 20 minutes at 4 °C
- Permeabilize with Triton X-100 1% in PBS 1X for 30 minutes at room temperature
- Block with BSA 3% in PBS 1X for 30 minutes at room temperature
- Incubate with primary antibody (Flavivirus 1:400; SARS-CoV-2 1:1,000) in blocking buffer for 1 hour at room temperature
- Incubate with HRP-conjugated secondary antibody (Flavivirus 1:10,000; SARS-CoV-2 1:5,000) for 1 hour at room temperature
- Add TMB substrate and incubate for 2–8 minutes until a bright blue color develops and stop reaction with 0.5 M H₂SO₄
- Measure absorbance at OD 450 nm using GloMax® Discover

5.3.2. Cell Viability Measurement

- Remove growth medium from each well without disturbing the cell monolayer
- Add CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 reagent (60 µL) directly to each well
- Incubate plates on an orbital shaker at 400 rpm for 10 min at room temperature, protected from light
- Transfer cell lysates (50 µL) to a white 96-well luminescence plate
- Measure luminescence using the GloMax® Discover Microplate Reader (Promega) with settings optimized for CellTiter-Glo assays as per manufacturer instructions
- Export the relative luminescence units (RLUs) values for data normalization and calculation of antiviral activity

6. Results Elaboration and Data Analysis

6.1. Data Processing

- Raw data obtained from ELISA-based assays or CellTiter-Glo® 2.0 assays) are collected for each well
- For ELISA-based assays, data are processed by normalizing absorbance values to appropriate control wells. Infected, untreated cells (virus control, VC) are used to define maximal viral replication, while uninfected, untreated cells (cell control, CC) are used to define background signal
- For CellTiter-Glo® assays, luminescence values are normalized using uninfected, untreated cells as cell control (CC, maximal cell viability) and infected, untreated cells as virus control (VC, maximal cytopathic effect)

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6.2. Antiviral Activity and IC₅₀ Determination

6.2.1. ELISA-based assays (DENV, ZIKV, WNV, SARS-CoV-2 in A549-AT)

- Antiviral activity is determined by comparing normalized absorbance values obtained from compound-treated wells with those of VC and CC wells
- Results are expressed as percentage inhibition of viral replication relative to controls
- Dose–response relationships are generated using the tested compound concentrations, and IC₅₀ values (compound concentration resulting in 50% inhibition of viral replication) are estimated using GraphPad software v.9.0

6.2.2. CellTiter-Glo® assays (SARS-CoV-2 in VERO E6)

- Antiviral activity is evaluated as protection from virus-induced cytopathic effect by comparing normalized cell viability values from compound-treated wells with VC and CC wells.
- Results are expressed as relative cell viability or percentage protection from cytopathic effect. Dose–response curves are generated, and IC₅₀ values are calculated using GraphPad software v.9.0.

7. Acceptance Criteria

The antiviral assay is considered valid if the following criteria are met:

- Virus control (VC) wells show consistent viral replication or cytopathic effect clearly distinguishable from cell control (CC) wells, with a difference of at least 1 log in relative luminescence units (RLU) or, in the case of ELISA-based readouts, a difference of ≥ 0.6 –0.7 optical density (OD) units between VC and CC
- Cell control (CC) wells display normal cell morphology and expected viability, with RLU or OD values falling within the established internal acceptance range. For RLU-based readouts, the CC value must show a minimum 1-log difference compared to the death control (corresponding to the VC in antiviral assays). For OD-based readouts, acceptable values range between 0.1 and 0.3.
- Reference compounds (sofosbuvir for flaviviruses and nirmatrelvir for SARS-CoV-2) show inhibitory activity consistent with internal historical data
- Variability among replicate wells is within acceptable limits, generally considered as CV% below 30%
- No evidence of microbial contamination or major technical issues are observed during the assay

8. Documentation and Archiving

- All raw data and calculated IC₅₀ values are recorded in laboratory records and archived according to internal procedures

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9. Annexes

9.1. Plate layout template

